

STUDIES IN SCURVY

BY

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To

Professors Axel Holst and Theodor Frölich

This work is respectfully inscribed by

THE AUTHOR

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Preface.

The work which is here presented was begun in July, 1922. It would have been impracticable to fulfil it without the possibilities of technical aid offered by clinical laboratories. To Professors F. HENSCHEN and G. HÄGGQUIST, who have allowed me to avail myself of these possibilities and to whom I am also indebted for much helpful advice, I beg to express my gratitude. My thanks are also due to Professors I. JUNDELL and U. QUENSEL, to Assistant Professor Dr. C. KLING, Doctors R. NORDGREN, G. VESTBECK, H. DAVIDE, A. WASSÉN, S. SIVE, A. WALLGREN, Å. ÅKERLUND, the Dental Surgeon Dr. G. WESTIN, and others, for various reasons, some of which I have mentioned more particularly in my book. Special thanks are due to Doctor F. WAHLGREN and Fil. Doctor L. G. ROMELL who have kindly read the proofs.

My late father, the historian NILS J. HÖJER, who during all his life, beside his practical activity as a teacher, devoted himself to scientific work for science's sake, has been my model. My wife, SIGNE HÖJER, has been my helper.

I have allowed myself as a respectful token of admiration to inscribe my work to Professors AXEL HOLST and THEODOR FRÖLICH in Christiania, the first investigators in the field of experimental scurvy, whose work still remains unrivalled. Even though the exaggeration is evident in Funk's utterance (1922): »Since the experiments of Holst and Frölich, no real progress has been made (in experimental scurvy), in spite of the numerous publications that have appeared», yet his words show how high Holst and Frölich's works rank among all the rest.

Hagalund, Sweden. February 1924.

J. Axel Höjer.

generally been misinterpreted, are described for teeth, endosomal and enchondral bone formation. For the connective tissue a general atrophy is described, which especially overtakes the collagen fibrils. This change is also proved in the vascular walls. In muscles, lymphoid tissue, liver, salivary gland, adrenal and kidney an atrophy combined with necrosis has been found. Also in these regions the tissues seem more severely struck, the more the scurvy is developed. It is established that some of the most active and most differentiated of the cells in the body are caught earliest and most severely by the scorbutic atrophy. The changes which have been described may be traced at a very early stage of the latent period. The importance of subjecting this latent stage to a close study is strongly emphasized.

Through these investigations the pathological picture of scurvy has thus been amplified, and the principal features of the disease have been analysed and found to be uniformly explainable.

PART IV.

Scurvy and tuberculosis.

CHAPTER I.

Historical review.

An importance of the diet to the progress of tuberculosis has been assumed already by LINNÉ. He writes in 1766: »Ingesta nimis nutrancia — nonne hinc saepissime oritur Phtisis juvenum?» On the contrary, subsequent investigators have as a rule regarded the general malnutrition as acting upon the progress of tuberculosis, though the problem up till the present time has evoked a comparatively small interest. CORNET and KOSSEL write in 1913: »Es ist wohl denkbar, dass ein abgekapselter Herd durch Unterernährung ausgelaugt und die Bacillen mobilisiert werden». The authors are evidently thinking of the theory of »demineralisation». LÖWENSTEIN, who in the

same textbook (KOLLE-WASSERMANN) writes the chapter on »Tuberkuloseimmunität«, is briefer still. In the first volume of BRAUER-SCHRÖDER-BLUMENFELD'S »Handbuch der Tuberkulose«, 1915, HANS MUCH writes a hundred pages about »Die Immunität«, without mentioning the influence of the food. FRIEDRICH MADSEN writes in the same volume about »Disposition und individuelle Prophylaxe«. He mentions the malnutrition only in passing and ends with some rules for the prophylaxis, which apply to the community and to the individual. The public measures include neutralizing of expectoration, hygien of the infants' milk, settling of the housing problem, sanatorium treatment for the severest cases, compulsory notification for the arranging of home disinfection and hospital nursing. The individual prophylactic measures are summarized thus:

- »1. Belehrung der Einzelnen über Infektionsgefahr.
2. Erziehung zur Reinlichkeit.
3. Abhaltung der minder Widerstandsfähigen von besonders gefährdeten Berufen.
4. Kräftigung aller durch Hygiene der Schule, Erziehung zum vernünftigen Sport u. s. w.»

What the author wishes to set forth with regard to the choice of suitable food will thus lie contained in the »u. s. w.« — No more does PHILIP (1922), apart from the zomotherapy, mention anything about the relation of different articles of food to tuberculosis.

Most of the systematic experiments on the subject that have been undertaken are devoted to this so-called zomotherapy. It originates in experiments by HÉRICOURT and RICHET (1900). These investigators found in the case of dogs inoculated with tuberculosis that a good effect was worked through injecting juice from raw meat. The zomotherapy consists in feeding through the mouth with larger or smaller quantities of juice pressed from raw meat. It has been praised by many (RAISSONNIER, JOSIAS, JOSIAS and ROUX, PHILIP), by others not (STEINITZ and WEIGERT). It does not seem to have been made much use of. Without entering into the question it

may only be pointed out, that all those who advocate it, indicate that the meat juice is effective only when raw. In this connection I may remark that BARLOW recommended raw meat juice as a good antiscorbutic in infantile scurvy.

Here I would like to mention in a few words an experiment which was made by me in the children's hospital »Samariten»¹ during the winter of 1916—1917. Twenty children of different ages with different kinds of tuberculosis, most of them with tuberculosis of the bronchial glands, were given a daily dose of 50—100 ccm. of raw blood serum each. The blood was gathered under certain precautions at the daily slaughtering of cattle in the slaughter-house of Stockholm and was placed in the freezing-room. The serum was taken up by pipet the following day and given to the children in cocoa. It was taken readily. The experiment went on for four months. The effect on the children's state of health seemed striking. Their appetite, colour and tonus improved, and the tuberculous process went rapidly towards healing, as far as could be judged clinically and by Roentgen rays. However, only a small number of the children remained in the hospital during the whole period of the experiment, and there was not a sufficient number of control patients, wherefore the experiment can not be said to have been conclusive.

Other experiments are few. In 1907, R. WEIGERT made experiments with different feeding of pigs infected with tuberculosis. These experiments are said to have shown that the animals fed on a diet rich in fat (whole milk and oil of sesame) resisted the tuberculosis better than those fed chiefly on carbohydrates (buttermilk and bran, potatoes). First of all the general condition was better, and then there was also a certain difference in the extent of the process. But the diets used differ also in other respects than fat and carbohydrates. The fat-rich diet must especially have held more A-vitamin. The experiments of THOMAS in 1913 only comprised 6 animals and gave ambiguous results. KARCZAG states

¹ Chief: Dr. R. NORDGREN, to whom my thanks are due for his kind assistance in the experiment.

in 1919, that his attempts to act on the tuberculosis allergy gave the same results in man and in guinea-pig. The two most important factors are light and abundant nutrition. The changes in the allergy, however, were not at all parallel with the progress of the tuberculosis. Albinoes, for instance, showed better allergy but succumbed sooner to death.

GERHARTZ undertook in 1922 experiments as to the influence of age on the progress of tuberculosis in guinea-pigs. He arrives at the conclusion that »es kann kein Zweifel bestehen, dass sich tierexperimentell eine Abhängigkeit der Tuberkulosekrankheitsdauer von Ernährungszustand und Alter des Tieres zur Zeit der Infektion auch bei exakter Anordnung des Versuches nicht erweisen lässt«. What is proved by Gerhartz' experiments is that with a dosage of infection calculated per 100 grams and with uniform dietary (we are not told which), the progress of guinea-pig tuberculosis is very heterogeneous, and that the differences seem independent of the age of the animals.

The increased spread of tuberculosis in Germany during and after the World War has stimulated the interest in that country in the question of a conjunction between food and tuberculosis. So far, however, the statements diverge.

W. STOELTZNER writes in 1920: »Dass die Tuberkulose seit dem Kriege bei uns in erschreckender Weise an Zahl und an Schwere zugenommen hat, ist allgemein bekannt. Ebenso ist wohl nicht daran zu zweifeln, dass die Kriegskost die wichtigste Ursache dessen ist. Ist nun das schädliche in der Kriegskost die quantitative Unterernährung oder ihre qualitative Eigenart?« On the ground of clinical experiences Stoeltzner answers the question thus: »Wahrscheinlich trägt das einseitige Vorwiegen der Kohlehydrate in der Kriegskost die Hauptschulde an dem Überhandnehmen der Tuberkulose«.

KIEFER says in 1922: »Alle die schönen Theorien über Disposition und Immunität, müssen nach den grossen Experimenten des Krieges, der Blockade, der Armut, gründlich revidiert werden«. He states that the tuberculosis in Germany has increased and assumed a more malignant character. Among

circumstances that determine the prognosis he mentions »die deletären Folgen der langdauernden Unterernährung»; among predisposing illnesses several, but not scurvy.

In ASCHOFF's large »Handbuch der ärztlichen Erfahrungen im Weltkrieg», vol. VIII, WEINERT writes about »phtisische Infektionen». He mentions various circumstances that may aggravate the progress of tuberculosis, even »Schussverletzungen», but does not mention scurvy. No more does BEITZKE, who in the same handbook writes about »fortschreitende Phtisen». Nor does ASCHOFF himself seem to have thought of any relation of cause and effect, when in his book »Skorbut, von L. ASCHOFF und W. KOCH», 1919, he says that among a material of 23 soldiers, dead of scurvy, he had found the majority (the number is not given) suffering from florid tuberculosis of different kinds: »Tuberkulose der serösen Höhlen, der Meningen, Miliartuberkulose, Lungen- und Darmptise.» Aschoff and Koch wish to see an explanation of this in the fact that the majority of the patients were Turks, in whom they assume a special predisposition for tuberculosis.

SELTNER und NEHRING, on the other hand, in 1921 subjected to a closer analysis the relation between the food and the increase of the tuberculosis death rate in Germany during the war — chiefly on account of the change in the curve for the tuberculosis death rate during the war in German towns with more than 30,000 inhabitants. The apex of the curve, instead of lying as otherwise in April, was during the years 1917—1919 advanced till May. From the interesting account I quote the following:

»Die Verschiebung nach dem Sommer hin spricht nicht dafür, dass klimatische Faktoren den allein entscheidenden Einfluss auf die Tuberkulosesterblichkeit haben. Ganz unerklärlich wäre dann auch die noch weitere Verschiebung von vier Wochen, auf Mitte Mai, in den Jahren 1917—1919, wo die Tuberkulösen, durch die Unterernährung geschwächt, eine erheblich geringere Widerstandsfähigkeit hätten haben müssen und infolgedessen die Höhepunkt der Sterblichkeit gerade in diesen Jahren früher zu erwarten gewesen wäre. Der monatliche Verlauf der Tuberku-

losesterblichkeitskurve scheint uns darauf hinzudeuten, dass neben den Witterungsverhältnissen im Winter und den dadurch bedingten Erkältungskrankheiten auch die Ernährung, die bekanntlich im Winter vom Monat zu Monat qualitativ schlechter wird, da sie, wenigstens bezüglich der Kohlehydrate immer mehr auf eingekellerte und konservierte Nahrungsmittel angewiesen ist, eine grosse Rolle spielt. *Man könnte an die Vitamine denken*¹, die für den Tuberkulösen vielleicht besonders wirkungsvoll sind. Im Beginn des Sommers, sobald die Zufuhr des frischen Gemüses einsetzt, sinkt die Sterblichkeit, erreicht im Herbst ihren tiefsten Stand und bleibt in den Friedensjahren (1914 und 1920) auch im ersten Teil des Winters auf einer niedrigen Stufe. Hierdurch könnte vielleicht auch die auffallende Verschiebung der Gipfel in den Jahren 1917—1919 erklärt werden, da durch die Gemeinbewirtschaftung und teilweise Rationierung der Gemüse die Versorgung der Bevölkerung hiermit erschwert und verzögert wurde.

Eine ausreichende Ernährung dient nicht nur dazu, den einzelnen Menschen wieder voll arbeits- und leistungsfähig zu machen, sie wird auch das wirksamste Mittel zur Bekämpfung der Tuberkulose sein.

Unter den sozialen Faktoren, welche auf die Tuberkulosesterblichkeit von Einfluss sind, sind zweifellos die Ernährungsverhältnisse am wichtigsten, wichtiger als die Wohnungsverhältnisse.»

A statement by KAISERLING to the same effect is quoted by ADAMS and HAMILTON:

»That the increased rate of tuberculosis (1917 and 1918) is due to food and not to other incidents of war, is shown by the slight rise before the tightening of the blockade and the rapid rise after it. German physicians are beginning to say, that tuberculosis should be regarded primarily not as an infectious disease but as a disease of nutrition, to be controlled much more by feeding than by preventing infection — —.»

ADAMS and HAMILTON add:

»In the wards for tubercular children we saw varieties of the disease which used to be regarded as medical curiosities, so extreme as to be seen only in primitive people with no racial immunity. Germany's racial immunity, if there really be such a thing, was destroyed by the blockade.»

¹ The italics are mine.

Remarkable is also GEOGHEGAN'S description from the West Indies. On the whole these islands have a rich vegetation, a relative prosperity and a varied diet. The climate is excellent. One group of islands, however, the Turk Islands, are conspicuous for the poverty of the inhabitants. Their food is as a whole limited in variety, inferior in nature, and deficient in freshness. Starchy foods predominate. While tuberculosis as a rule is but little spread in the West-Indian archipelago, the Turk Islands have a predominance of tuberculosis.

In his excellent monography on scurvy, of 1920, which has been frequently quoted above, HESS writes, p. 88: »Active tuberculosis is a not uncommon secondary manifestation», and p. 99: »Tuberculous lesions are also frequently present, and are stated to assume fresh activity as the result of the nutritional disorder.»

The best support for such a supposition is given by the material of scorbutic patients, over which SALLE and ROSENBERG report in 1921. In different groups the figures for complicating tuberculosis were 9—22 %. All their deaths were due to tuberculosis, often in its miliar form. Out of 461 cases of scurvy, 17 died, that is, 3.6 per cent. Salle and Rosenberg speak with great assuredness of the mutual relation between scurvy and tuberculosis:

»Wenn somit die Tuberkulose einer Skorbutentwicklung die Wege ebnet, so bedeutet andererseits das Hinzutreten von Skorbut zur Tuberkulose häufig eine sehr ernst zu nehmende Komplikation. Wir erwähnten schon, dass bei unseren sämtlichen Todesfällen Tuberkulose die Todesursache war. Wie diese deletäre Wechselwirkung zu deuten ist, ist unklar. Klinisch war bei einer grossen Anzahl der Fälle der progrediente unaufhaltsam zum Tode führende Charakter der Tuberkulose ebenso auffallend, wie die häufig schlechte Beeinflussbarkeit skorbutischer Symptome durch sonst sicher wirkende diätetische Massnahmen.»

It can not but strike us, how many of the more closely examined cases of infantile scurvy have been complicated by a florid tuberculosis. Thus it was, for instance, in three of SCHOEDEL'S five cases, one of INGIER'S three, in SCHMORL'S and NÄGELI'S children and one of HART and LESSING'S five monkeys.

As to the question, on the other hand, about the influence of tuberculosis on the onset of scurvy, BIERICH gives a negative verdict. He finds this on a very large material, 1,343 cases of scurvy patients, of whom more than 10 per cent. were tubercular. He says briefly that the tuberculosis does not seem to have had any predisposing influence on the onset of scurvy.

These statements and experiences of a connection between tuberculosis and scurvy, or a lack of fresh vegetables, are of the very greatest interest. A factor which somewhat lessens their cogency is, that persons who die of scurvy often also (see p. 139) have suffered from the want of other substances than the antiscorbutic. A-vitamin will often have been lacking in the food, which will probably also in other respects have been insufficient.

In the literature I have found but one attempt at experimentally elucidating the question of scurvy and tuberculosis. MOURIQUAND and MICHEL, who in 1921 state that they have found the injection of thyroid extract to turn a latent scurvy into manifest, mention in a note that one of them together with a deceased physician, Ménard, has occupied himself with experiments in order to find out whether tuberculosis might have a similar influence.¹

In 1920 I pointed out the high A-vitamin contents of the cod-liver oil and the dairy products as a possible explanation of the high esteem in which of old they are held in the tuberculosis therapy, compared to other fats. The relation of A-vitamin to tuberculosis, as a matter of fact, is also well worth experimental testing.² In the course of my experiments I

¹ MOURIQUAND, MICHEL and BERTOYE in 1922 published the negative results. They gave also a preliminary note of experiments aimed to elucidate the influence of scurvy on the progress of tuberculosis. The experiments had not given conclusive results.

² Already in 1907, WELLS will have seen a favourable effect on the tuberculosis in pigs of feeding with cod-liver oil. HAPP and WAGNER studied 1923 the question clinically in infants and KASSOWITZ in elder children, without conclusive results. For the present, M. SMITH is engaged in such experiments on guinea-pigs, of which he in 1923 gave a first communication.

have subjected the C-vitamin to such testing. I have gone along two lines. First I have tried to investigate the mutual relation of scurvy and tuberculosis in guinea-pigs. Then I have also attempted clinically to test the influence of the antiscorbutic on the progress of tuberculosis in man. The latter investigation, however, is chiefly to be looked upon as a preliminary of future research on a larger scale.

CHAPTER II.

Experimental studies on guinea-pig.

Technique and survey of experiment.

(Records of cases see p. 206.)

The experiment was carried out between March 29th and July 3rd, 1923. 86 guinea-pigs were used for the purpose; 62 of them were bought from a private breeder in the first half of February at the age of two weeks and were fed by me on complete dietary (cereal, bran, milk, swedes) for more than seven weeks. The remaining 26 were bought on March 17th from an institution and were fed nearly two weeks on complete dietary by me, as they had earlier been in the institution. The first weighing of the animals was undertaken March 19th and 20th.

WALLGREN, after experiments on rabbits, is very exacting with regard to the choice of animals for tuberculosis experiments. He claims that they should all be of the same age and preferably of the same litter. As for guinea-pigs, however, GERHARTZ has not been able to demonstrate any influence of different ages on the progress of tuberculosis. The lifetime after the injection of a certain dosage of tubercle bacilli is very different for these animals, and the same thing applies to animals of the same litter that have the same dietary. This ought to be borne in mind when judging the experiments. But it does not by any means prevent the use of guinea-pigs as experimental animals in tuberculosis experiments as long as the results are judged with due discrimination.

Half the number of experimental animals were infected on March 29th, 1923, with the same dosage of tubercle bacilli, 0.00005 gram. The bacilli were obtained in a homogeneous emulsion from the Public Medical Institute. They were of its stock No. 80, human type, indicated of low virulence, and came from a culture a fortnight old. The injection was made intramuscularly into the adductors on the inner posterior side of the right thigh. During the first twenty-four hours after the injection the animals were somewhat dishevelled and felt hot. After another twenty-four hours, they could not be distinguished from the controls as far as appearance and liveliness went.

GRÜNER and HAMBURGER indicate a somewhat lower dosage of tubercle bacilli (0.000005 gram) as a suitable dosage of infection in experimental studies on guinea-pigs, and JOEST and EMHOFF have used a still smaller dosage (0.000001 gram).¹ In order to determine a suitable dosage of stock No. 80, I made a preliminary experiment, seven animals (No. 13—19) having been injected with doses on a sinking scale from 0.0025 to 0.0000005 gram. According to the outcome of this experiment the dosage was fixed to 0.00005 gram.

The animals were divided into groups, with 8 (7) animals in each, the groups receiving different dietary from the day of injection. In each group half the number were tubercularly infected. Yet the animals on complete dietary of cereal, bran, 60 ccm. of unboiled milk and fresh swedes, were 16 in number, of which 8 were tubercularly infected. 8 of the animals had scorbutic diet (see p. 12). The remaining 65 had the same scorbutogenetic basal diet and besides different doses of preserved orange juice. This latter I had prepared immediately before the experiment by pressing the juice of fresh juicy oranges, pouring it into smaller bottles of 200 grams, which were warmed, stoppered and boiled during 30 minutes immersed in water. The dosage of the juice and the grouping of the animals are shown in detail by Table 6. Since the experiment indicated that the minimum protective dose

¹ M. SMITH used a larger dose (0,0005 gram).

Table 6.

Division of guinea-pigs within different groups.

Dietary per day and animal.	Fraction of m. pr. d. of anti-scorbutic	Numbers of animals not infected with tuberculosis	Numbers of animals infected with tuberculosis
Complete mixed dietary	More than 1.0	97. 98. 99. 100.	104. 105. 106. 107.
		101. 102. 103. 183	108. 109. 110. 111
Scurvy dietary = Sc.	0	112. 113. 114. 115	116. 117. 118. 119
Sc + 0.3 ccm. pres. orange juice	0.1	120. 121. 122. 123	124. 125. 126. 127
Sc. + 0.6 " " "	0.2	128. 129. 130. 131	132. 133. 134
" + 1.0 " " "	0.3	135. 136. 137. 138	139. 140. 141. 142
" + 1.5 " " "	0.5	143. 144. 145. 146	147. 148. 149. 150
" + 2.0 " " "	0.7	151. 152. 153. 154	155. 156. 157. 158
" + 2.5 " " "	0.8	159. 160. 161. 162	163. 164. 165. 166
" + 3.5 " " "	More than 1.0	167. 168. 169. 170	171. 172. 173. 174
" + 5.0 " " "	More than 1.0	175. 176. 177. 178	180. 181. 182
		179	

(m. pr. d.) of this juice was larger than 2.5 ccm. and smaller than 3.5 ccm., it has been approximately fixed at 3 ccm., and the quantity of antiscorbutic given to each group has been calculated accordingly as fraction of the minimum protective dose. The inaccuracy involved in this estimating of the m. pr. d. may be put to ± 0.5 ccm. = 17 %. This relative figure is also applicable to the fractions of the m. pr. d. With the uncertainty which is still incident to the upper limit of the range of scurvy (see p. 126) the most important thing, however, is not the absolute figure, but the relative value of the doses in the different groups.

The tubercular animals that died during the course of the experiment or were chloroformed at the conclusion after ninety odd days, in all 42, were examined macro- and microscopically. For determining the degree of scurvy, teeth and ribs were

Table 7.

Survey of experiments.

Abbreviations and terms the same as in the table on p. 18.

Series	Number	Diet	Weight in grams		Scurvy	Infected with tbc	Lifetime days	Remarks
			initial	final				
XXIV	97	Complete dietary	165	250	0	0	52	{Died of bronchopneumonia ac. Killed
	98		150	460	0	0	96	
	99		245	545	0	0	96	»
	100		230	560	0	0	96	»
	101		160	445	0	0	96	»
	102		130	575	0	0	96	»
	103		200	515	0	0	96	»
XXV	104		150	665	0	*	93	»
	105		300	560	0	*	93	»
	106		200	570	0	*	93	»
	107		180	210	0	*	29	
	108	290	490	0	*	93	Killed	
	109	250	540	0	*	93	»	
	110	260	550	0	*	93	»	
111	290	430	0	*	70			
XXVI	112	Basal scorbutic diet = sc. pr. d.	390	235	****	0	28	
	113		390	260	(****)	0	19	
	114		410	410	****	0	1	
	115		390	260	****	0	29	
	116		445	360	****	*	18	
	117		545	335	****	*	33	
	118		495	390	****	*	36	
119	470	280	****	*	24			
XXVII	120	Sc. + 0.1 m. pr. d.	370	270	***	0	15	{Drowned in the milk basin
	121		375	280	***	0	25	
	122		390	230	***	0	42	
	123		360	210	***	0	32	

Series	Number	Diet	Weight in grams		Scurvy	Infected with tbc	Lifetime days	Remarks
			initial	final				
XXVIII	124	Sc. + 0.1 m. pr. d.	460	270	***	*	23	
	125		425	310	***	*	58	Died of pneumonia ac.
	126		425	315	***	*	43	
	127		410	28	***	*	17	Died of pneumonia ac.
	128	Sc. + 0.2 m. pr. d.	405	270	**	0	15	Colitis ac.
	129		390	310	**	0	22	Gastroduodenit. ac.
	130		370	290-	**	0	29	
	131		370	290	***	0	21	
	132	Sc. + 0.2 m. pr. d.	450	270	***	*	43	
	133		440	330	***	*	86	
	134		410	350-	**	*	6	{Died of pneumonia + necrosis ac. pancreat.
	135		415	360	**	0	83	{Abscessus lienis rupturatus " " et hepatis
	136	Sc. + 0.3 m. pr. d.	425	370-	**	0	64	
	137		385	265-	**	0	37	
138	270		285	**	0	40		
139	460		480	**	*	77	Died of ruptura lienis	
140	395		320-	**	*	43		
141	360		350-	**	*	52		
142	375		275	**	*	76		
143	340		245	**	0	59	Died of septicemia	
XXX	144	Sc. + 0.5 m. pr. d.	395	540	*	0	92	Killed
	145		370	230	*	0	18	
	146		270	395	*	0	92	Killed
	147		430	295	*	*	32	
	148	380	340	**	*	56		
	149	425	380	**	*	92	Killed	
	150	395	265	*	*	28		
	151	355	500	*	0	92	Killed	
XXXI	152	Sc. + 0.7 m. pr. d.	270	250	*	0	22	
	153		375	420	*	0	90	Died of pleuropneumonia
	154		310	280-	*	0	6	
	155		410	280	*	*	19	Ulcus duodeni
	156		405	435	*	*	92	Killed

Series	Number	Diet	Weight in grams		Scurvy	Infected with the	Lifetime days	Remarks
			initial	final				
XXXI	157	Sc + 0.7 m. pr. d.	355	265	*	*	22	
	158		312	210	*	*	40	
	159		345	275	*	0	29	Died of gastroenterocolitis ac. Killed
160	350	580	*	0	92			
XXXII	161	Sc + 0.8 m. pr. d.	325	520	*	0	92	»
	162		355	520	*	0	92	»
	163		270	280	*	*	11	
	164		410	325	*	*	44	
	165		410	410	*	*	90	
	166		295	210	*	*	89	
XXXIII	167	Sc + 1.2 m. pr. d.	315	220	0	0	12	Died of appendicitis ac.
	168		325	475	0	0	93	Killed
	169		290	440	0	0	93	»
	170		335	470	0	0	93	»
	171		365	445	0	*	93	»
XXXIV	172	Sc + 1.7 m. pr. d.	325	340	0	*	24	Died of pneumonia ac.
	173		350	430	0	*	89	Ruptura lienis
	174		280	230	0	*	42	
	175		150	145	0	0	17	
	176		155	240	0	0	75	Pneumonia, peritonit. ac.
	177		180	215	0	0	28	Bronchopneumonia
	178		250	620	0	0	93	Killed
XXXV	179	Complete dietary 40 gr. wheat + 6 cc. orange juice, 2.0 m. pr. d.	240	440	0	*	93	» , pneumonia ac.
	180		290	310	0	*	38	Died of » »
	181		200	450	0	*	93	Killed
	182		265	380	0	*	93	»
	183		330	515	0	0	96	Killed. Had for some time beriberi-like symptoms
184	380	270	0	0	8			
XXXV	185	Complete dietary	235	150	0	0	14	
	186		300	200	0	0	11	
	187		250	160	0	0	7	
	188		280	280	0	0	11	Killed
	189		340	340	0	0	1	»

principally examined. For the study of the tuberculosis, the attention was chiefly directed to the local focus in the thigh musculature, regional lymph-glands, spleen and liver. The other organs were examined microscopically as far as the macroscopical examination gave reason for supposing changes within them. Lungs and lymph-glands other than the regional ones have thus been examined in most cases. Six local foci in the thigh musculature (No. 119, 125, 126, 127, 155, 171) are not noted in the records of the macroscopic examination. One of these (Case 171), was found in series of sections at microscopical examination, whereas in three (Cases 119, 127 and 155), pictures were had from the immediate vicinity of the necrosis. Microscopic pictures are lacking from the primary focus in Cases 106, 148. For the regional lymph-glands microscopical examination is lacking in 6 cases, No. 107, 116, 134, 139, 155, 166; for the spleen in one case, No. 157. The reason for this incompleteness of the microscopical examination, which, however, is of no very great importance to the study, the material being so large, was a misunderstanding between the author and the technical aid. The number of the examined sections also for this latter part of the examination still is greater than 1,500. They have been stained in three ways, all with hematoxylin-eosin, the majority also with Hansen's connective-tissue stain, and with Ziehl's carbol-fuchsin on tubercle bacilli. For specific cases other special staining methods, mentioned on p. 32, have been used.

Influence of scurvy on tuberculosis.

gress of tuberculosis. The weight charts are found on pp. 207—233. They show that in general the curves of the tubercular animals follow those of the control animals, the lifetime seeming in most cases to be determined by the antiscorbutic dose. Series 32 is an exception (daily dose 0.8 m. pr. d.), p. 225, in which series three of the controls were alive at the conclusion of the experiment, but none of the tubercular animals. One of these died of general tuberculosis on the 90th day after the injection.

Out of the 15 tuberculized animals that had an antiscorbutic dose large enough to protect them from all scorbutic pathological changes (Series 25, 33 and 34), 9 animals, or 60 %, were alive at the conclusion of the experiment after 93 days. Out of 16 animals not infected, 12, or 75 %, were alive. The death rate for the tubercular animals was thus a little higher. Two of these dead animals had general tuberculosis (No. 174 after 42 days, No. 111 after 70 days). In one case (No. 173, 89 days) the cause of death was rupture of the spleen, which was changed tubercularly.

The progress of the tuberculosis was fairly uniform. Thus, 24 of the 25 animals that lived more than 40 days showed tuberculous changes, besides locally in the muscle, in the regional glands, spleen and liver, also in one or more other organs. One animal on complete dietary, No. 171, showed no clinical symptoms of tuberculosis, and no macroscopic changes when killed after three months. In series of sections from the thigh musculature the miliary primary focus was found, fibrously healed; no tubercle bacilli were demonstrable.

Among the animals that died during the first 40 days of the experiment, the extent of the tuberculosis was more heterogeneous, as is seen from Table 8.

Table 8.

The extent of tuberculosis in animals, dead after a different number of days since beginning of experiment, having had different doses of antiscorbutic, counted in ccm. of preserved orange juice, and in fractions of m. pr. d. The numbers are those of the animals in the Records.

Abbreviations:

- 10 = tuberculosis found in the place of injection in the thigh musculature and in regional lymph-glands;
 1i = besides in the primary focus also in the spleen;
 h = besides in the primary focus also in the liver;
 u = the found also in other places than the primary focus, liver and spleen.

Dietary	Fraction of m. pr. d. anti- scurbutic	Days		
		10—20	20—30	30—40
Sc = scorbutic diet. . . .	0	116 u	119 u	117 li h 118 u
» + 0.3 ccm pres. or. j	0.1	127 li	124 u	—
» + 1.5 » » » »	0.5	—	150 u	147 u
» + 2 » » » »	0.7	155 o	157 lo	—
» + 2.5 » » » »	0.8	163 u	—	—
» + 3.5 » » » »	>1.0	—	172 u	—
» + 5 » » » »	>1.0	—	—	180 li h
Complete dietary	>1.0	—	107 o	—

It is seen from the Records that the number of microscopically examined organs is not the same for the different animals, and also that this can not explain the differences noted. That the different progress can no more be explained as owing to the different degree of scurvy, is also immediately evident from the table. Yet it is remarkable that the tuberculosis in the animals with pure scurvy dietary showed a larger extent than in many of the rest, and also that among these four animals suffering from scorbut gravior there was one, No. 118, where already after 36 days caseous glands were found in the hilus of liver and lung, a change not seen in any of the other ten animals.

A similar difference in the extent of tuberculosis in guinea-pigs is found by Gerhartz, who no more than the present writer considered that it could be explained by the different age or sex of the animals. In my experiments the C-vitamin has been varied without conclusive effect. Possibly a more distinct result would have been gained if a smaller dose of tubercle bacilli had been injected. The supply of A-vitamin has been practically constant. Among the factors that may have varied in my experiments, I mention:

- 1) the hereditary conditions of the animals;
- 2) the dietary of the mother during pregnancy and suckling;

- 3) other conditions during the first weeks;
- 4) the place of the injection of tubercle bacilli (more or less superficially; into or between muscular bundles; with or without opening blood or lymph vessels);
- 5) the pressure at the injection;
- 6) intercurrent acute infections, not always easy to diagnose.

The changes found in the 15 animals that had a complete dose of antiscorbutic agree with those described by earlier writers. The primary focus in the musculature was bounded by a rind of connective tissue more than a millimeter thick. It was also penetrated by connective tissue. This connective tissue was seen also at the microscopical examination to penetrate with its extraordinarily strong collagen fibrils the necrotic primary focus in the musculature (Plate III) as well as other tuberculous foci (Plate V). Near the primary focus there were seen muscle fibres, parts of which were necrotized and to a large extent calcified. There was also an increase of fibroblasts. Also in the primary focus itself as well as in the regional lymph-glands and often in the spleen, extensive calcifications are seen. This finding is different to that of RÖMER who in his large material only saw two guinea-pigs with calcification of tuberculous foci. The extensive calcification may perhaps be placed in connection with the small virulence in our stock of bacilli. In Case 104, typical Langhans' giant cells were seen in the primary muscle focus, the protoplasm of which was for the greater part calcified. About the genesis of these cells there has been disputes. The above-mentioned observation I interpret as favouring the conception that these giant cells are results of a beginning degeneration (BAUMGARTEN a. o.). The pictures do not give the impression of a calcium lump absorbed by the giant cell from the outside, but of a diffuse calcification of the protoplasm of the cell.

Character of the tuberculous changes.

In spleen and liver there was typical tuberculous granulation tissue, but of different character; necroses, as has already earlier been described by others, dominating in the spleen

picture, and a cirrhosis in the liver picture. In the spleen the tubercle bacilli were more numerous than in the liver, but also in each liver with an incipient cirrhosis bacilli were found, with some few exceptions, already in the first or second preparation. At such a change in the liver which may justly be called a cirrhosis tuberculosa, there are seen regenerative strands of young liver columns, fibroblasts with cells of different types, epithelioid cells and giant cells, part irregular, part of Langhans' type. It has earlier been described in guinea-pigs by STOERK, and afterwards by GOUGEROT, KLING and LICHTENSTEIN. It is of the greatest interest to note this constant reaction of the guinea-pig liver to slight tubercular infection, especially in view of the elucidation it may give to certain liver cirrhoses in children with slight tubercular infection (older writers, reported by Höjer). It was a striking circumstance that in the tuberculous foci, besides typical Langhans' giant-cells, there were also often found atypical such cells, and among them many that were more like the type described by STERNBERG. Since in my material tubercle bacilli of a not very virulent stock were injected, possibly (LICHTENSTEIN) pictures like those in lymphogranulomatosis STERNBERG—PALTAUF might be expected. A great number of the lymph-glands were uniformly swelled without macroscopically visible foci, but at the microscopical examination epithelioid cells and tubercle bacilli were found in them. Neither the macroscopic nor the microscopic picture otherwise resembled that shown in Sternberg's lymphogranulomatosis. In the granulation tissue no eosinophile cells or »mast-cells» were found, nor were any plasm-cells found by staining according to Pappenheim.

At the macroscopical examination of the tubercular animals that had severe scurvy, an essential difference from the picture just described was at once conspicuous. The tuberculous foci in muscle, lymph-gland or spleen were not seen to be surrounded or penetrated by any connective tissue (Plates IV and VI). The necrotic parts passed without such demarcation into non-tubercular tissue. Besides this lack of reactive tissue, where such might be expected, there were found, together with the par-

enchymatous atrophy of the organs in question, also the atrophy already described of the connective tissue, present before the onset of scurvy in muscle tendons, trabeculae of lymph-glands and spleen, vessels, etc. The material was stained, for the microscopical examination, with hematoxylin-eosin through which the cell form appears distinctly, and also to a large extent according to Hansen with trioxihematin for the study of the collagen tissue. In both series these changes were marked. They both showed that in the animals standing between those purely scorbutic and those fed on full dietary the connective tissue had a different character, which more or less approached the two extremes according to the scorbutic dose given to the animal. The result of the examination of the preparations is found in Table 9.

In this table the development of the connective tissue is indicated in five degrees, by C 0—C 4, thus:

- C 0*: no connective tissue reaction around or within the tuberculous foci. Especially there are no collagen fibrils in cells which might be interpreted as fibroblasts. At the same time there is in the old connective tissue a specially pronounced atrophy of the collagen substance.
- C 1*: thin layers and strands of fibroblasts appear. These fibroblasts seem to form collagen substance, though not in long fibrils but like a lump near the nucleus or an irregular ball of short threads. The cells do not seem placed in any marked order.
- C 2*: pronounced tendency to a parallelism between the cells mentioned. For the rest like *C 1*.
- C 3*: the fibroblasts have normal appearance, are arranged as in normal cases around and in the tuberculous foci, and form elongated collagen fibrils. The connective tissue is tender, however, both macro- and microscopically.
- C 4*: strong, rindlike, normal connective tissue with strong collagen fibrils in and about the tuberculous foci. No

Table 9.

The degree of fibrous reaction of the connective tissue in and around tuberculous foci in animals, dead a different number of days after beginning of experiment, and given different doses of antiscorbutic, counted as fraction of minimum protective dose (m. pr. d.). This dose is fixed at 3 cm. of the orange juice used (see p. 151). The numbers are those in the Records, p. 206. The strength of the reaction is expressed in 5 degrees (C0—C4), explained p. 161.

Fraction of m. pr. d. antiscorb.	Number of days from beginning of experiment till death of the animal									
	10—20	20—30	30—40	40—50	50—60	60—70	70—80	80—90	more than 90	
0	116 C 0	119 C 0	117 C 0 118 C 0							
0.1	127 0—1	124 0—1		126 0—1	125 0—1					
0.2				132 C 2				133 C 2		
0.3				140 C 2	141 C 1—2		139 C 3 142 C 2—3			
0.5		150 C 2	147 C 2		148 C 2				149 C 2	
0.7		157 C 2		158 C 2—3					156 C 2—3	
0.8	163 C 1—2			164 C 3				165 C 3 166 C 3		
1.2		172 C 3—4		174 C 4				173 C 4		
1.7			180 C 4						181 C 4 182 C 4	
free						111 C 4				104 C 4; 108 C 4 105 C 4; 109 C 4 106 C 4; 110 C 4

signs of atrophy visible in the connective tissue formed before the onset of scurvy.

This gradual deterioration of the collagen connective tissue manifests itself both in shape and colour. The collagen fibrils grow shorter, less regular, are often in a certain portion near the nucleus seen to be thicker than normally, or else as if they had lost their elongated form and had rolled up there. The colour is changed from the normal sparkling red, becomes a lighter pink, without gloss, and finally yellow.

It will be seen that in several cases I have hesitated to which degree to assign the strength of the connective tissue reaction. It is not always possible to decide whether the connective-tissue formation met with is pre-formed or newly-formed. The transitions between the stages fixed by me are not distinct. Often the reaction at the primary focus has been found to correspond to a certain degree, while lymph-glands afflicted later have shown a lower degree. The difference between the tendency to connective-tissue formation in different organs is also everywhere manifest, and thus the comparison must not be made directly between different organs but with the pictures given at normal connective tissue reaction of the organ in question. The figures for the strength of the reaction are therefore to a certain extent approximate. Without being stretched too far they confirm in any case in a striking manner what might already be surmised at the *post-mortem* examination, that *the strength of the connective-tissue reaction after a certain time is in a direct ratio to the dose of antiscorbutic given*. It will also seem as if for a certain case the strength of the connective-tissue reaction after a certain minimum time, about one month, were generally dependent, not so much on the lifetime after the injection, as rather on the size of the antiscorbutic dose. Here the connective tissue affords a parallel to what was proved above for the dentin. Finally it is evident, that a connective-tissue reaction of normal strength does not set in even in the latent stage (10 animals), not even with a dose of 0.8 m. pr. d. after three months. Only when the

dose of antiscorbutic given corresponds to a completely protective dose, there is a connective-tissue reaction, the strength of which is comparable to that appearing in animals on the complete control dietary (13 animals).

This connective-tissue reaction is comparatively easy to fix, thanks to the specific staining methods. About the organic changes in animals with scurvy and tuberculosis I can be brief. They are extraordinarily diversified. In the spleen, for instance, often a hundred times heavier than normally, hemorrhage, hemosiderosis, atrophy of the lymphoid tissue, hyperplasia of the reticulum, necroses, calcification, and specific granulation tissue, are all intermingled into pictures that have no resemblance to normal spleen tissue. I lack the qualifications for treating these changes in detail, nor is it in this connection necessary so to do.

Influence of tuberculosis on scurvy.

The constant presence of hemorrhages round the tuberculous foci is mentioned above (p. 112).

Besides hemorrhages, also necroses are seen near tuberculous foci, and especially small calcified necroses of muscle fibres are common in the thigh musculature of animals with scurvy and tuberculosis. Here there is, however, a change which may be seen as well with simple scurvy, though in that case not localized exactly here, as also with tuberculosis in otherwise healthy animals. It may seem probable that both diseases co-operate. Such a combination might also be supposed with regard to the appearance of necroses in the musculature in general and in the adrenals (see p. 74, 104), but we have no conclusive proof of this.

It is fairly common with extensive tuberculosis in scorbutic guinea-pigs to find granulation foci in the marrow of the ribs more or less close to the epiphyseal line. Here we often find a picture which macroscopically altogether agrees with that given by MOURIQUAND and MICHEL of the scorbutic

changes in the epiphyses. A microscopical examination at once makes it clear that this is a quite different process.

An examination of the question whether the tuberculosis, within the groups that are represented in the table 7, page 153, has aggravated the scorbutic symptoms and caused the animals to enter another stage of scurvy than that of the controls, shows that it can have been so only with regard to animals No. 148 and 149. Both these animals after 56 and 92 days have presented a scorbut extensus, whereas among the other animals with the same antiscorbutic dose two that had tuberculosis, dead after 28 and 32 days, and 3 controls, dead after 18, 92 and 92 days, respectively, only showed a scorbut levior. The fourth control animal, however, that died of septicemia after 59 days, also had scorbut extensus. Summarizing, it may be said, that the tuberculosis has shown no marked influence on the moment for the appearance of the scorbutic symptoms in different organs. When the opposite has been clinically observed (SALLE and ROSENBERG), this is probably due to a tuberculous intestinal affection with diarrhea. That in such cases antiscorbutic, given *per os*, does not show the expected effect has been stated for certain. Concerning the interpretation of this circumstance, see p. 117. For such cases the antiscorbutic may be administered otherwise than *per os* (HESS).

It may be remarked that animals 16 and 18, which had access to complete dietary but suffered from a general tuberculosis and had not increased in weight during the last month, showed slight scorbutic changes when the teeth were histologically examined. The animals were observed to eat cereal, but have probably not eaten enough of the swedes. In these cases the tuberculosis has thus indirectly caused scurvy, probably through the lessened appetite.

CHAPTER III.

Experiments on human subjects.

(Records of cases see p. 234.)

Hess says in his book: »In all nutritional investigation it should never be forgotten, that conclusions drawn from experiments on animals are merely provisional and must await substantiation on man, and furthermore, that, where differences in reaction are noted, the clinical data should be accorded full consideration.» In order further to investigate the question of the influence of scurvy on the course of tuberculosis, I have therefore carried out an experiment on human beings. In the experiment the following principle was adopted.

In a hospital for tuberculosis patients, where the diet might be suspected not to contain a completely protective dose of antiscorbutic, a number of patients (44) have been selected. I have taken them two and two together, trying to get patients as similar as possible in each couple as far as concerns age, sex, the extent and virulence of the tuberculous process, and the treatment. During the time of the year when the food in the North is most deficient in antiscorbutic, the months of March, April, and May, one of the two patients in each couple has had an orange a day added to his diet, while the other one has been given a specially prepared pastry. The clinical progress of the tuberculosis in the different cases has then been studied and compared. No immunity examinations have been made in this connection.

The experiment has been carried out in the Väsby Sanatorium in Uppland. This sanatorium has such an isolated situation that the supply of provisions from without could be controlled. For the permission to undertake the experiment at Väsby I am indebted to the Head Physician of the institutions at that place, Dr. HÅKANSSON. The physician of the Sanatorium, Dr. GUNNAR WESTBECK, has chosen the patients, made the examinations, written down the records, estimated the progress. For this and for his ungrudging and self-sacri-

feing assistance in the whole of the experiment I owe him my best thanks.

The dietary of the Sanatorium is as follows:

At 7.30 a. m. gruel and bread
 » 10 » breakfast
 » 12 noon milk
 » 1.30 p. m. dinner
 » 4.30 » coffee with rusks or white bread
 » 7 » supper.

The 70 patients of the Sanatorium (of which half the number have been selected for the experiment; the children are in a special department) consume on an average 2 litres of milk a day each. No fixed schedule of food is followed, but careful annotations are made daily of what is served, and from these annotations I have made the following extracts. Of food that might be considered to contain antiscorbutic, there has been provided during the time March 1st—May 31st 1923 (92 days):

Potatoes for *no* meal 5 days, for *one* meal 52 days, for *two* meals 35 days, in the last-mentioned case, often for one of the meals first boiled and then also fried.

Beet-root 17 times, always together with potatoes.

Beef-tea with vegetables 6 times.

Mashed roots 4 times, swedes 1 time, always together with potatoes.

Cabbage-soup 2 times, vegetable soup 2 times.

Chive 3 times.

Pears 1 time.

Among courses which for one reason or another may be considered rather unimportant as far as the supplying of antiscorbutic is concerned, may be mentioned red whortleberry jam (with Yorkshire pudding) 31 times, rhubarb mould 9 times, apple tart (dried apples) etc. 10 times, other fruit moulds 9 times, fruit-syrup sauce 3 times.

For every breakfast and supper are served vegetable margarine, hard rye-bread and cheese, rather rich, as much as is wished. Meat in some form is given once or twice daily.¹

The dietary may be characterized as plenteous, and complete in every respect except with regard to antiscorbutic. As providing this substance there are first of all to be mentioned milk and potatoes. During this time of the year (in 1923, the cows were not turned out to grass till after the conclusion of my experiments, in June) the milk is very deficient in antiscorbutic. To arrive at a definite estimation of the quantity of antiscorbutic supplied in 2 litres of milk, is not practicable. Potatoes also are a weak antiscorbutic and do not have any

Table 10.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Couple	Number	Age, years	Duration of experiment, days	Stage of tuberculosis	Progress	Progress of orange case compared to control
a	1 Or.	33	89	III*	n	—
	2	32	93	III	+	
b	3 Or.	35	24	III*	n	+ ?
	4	23	60	III	—	
c	5 Or.	21	93	III	+	+
	6	20	93	III	—	
d	7 Or.	53	75	II—III*	+	+
	8	48	93	I—II	n	
e	9 Or.	44	91	III*	+	+
	10	34		I—II	n	
f	11 Or.	29	93	III	+	+
	12	28	93	III*	—	
g	13 Or.	27	91	III	+	+
	14	20	93	III	n	

¹ Meat most often given as mince-meat, first fried and then boiled.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Couple	Number	Age, years	Duration of experiment, days	Stage of tuberculosis	Progress	Progress of orange case compared to control
h	15 Or.	43	93	III*	+	+
	16	33	93	III	—	
i	17 Or.	25	93	III	n	+
	18	21	93	III	—	
k	19 Or.	32	93	III	+	+
	20	63	67	III	—	
l	21 Or.	20	93	II*	+	+
	22	16	93	I—II	n	
m	23 Or.	18	93	I	n	=
	24	24	93	I—II*	n	
n	25 Or.	12	77	I	n	+?
	26	16	93	I	n?	
o	27 Or.	24	93	II*	+	+
	28	28	93	I—II	n	
p	29 Or.	25	93	III*	+	+
	30	26	93	III	n	
q	31 Or.	27	93	III	+	+
	32	16	93	III	n	
r	33 Or.	7	93	III*	+	=
	34	25	93	III	+	
s	35 Or.	10	93	I	+	+
	36	11	93	I*	n	
t	37 Or.	8	92	I	+	+
	38	11	93	I	—	
u	39 Or.	4	93	I	n	=
	40	3	29	I	n	
v	41 Or.	4	93	I	+	
	42	—	— ¹	—		
w	43 Or.	12	55	I	+	+
	44	4	93	I	—	

¹ Discharged shortly after the beginning of the experiment.

considerable importance as such till consumed in rather large quantities. In any case the dietary is poor in fresh vegetables, roots and fruit.

The dietary of the children comprises an egg a day, and 3 dessert-spoonfuls of cod-liver oil.

The patients are not weighed naked, and therefore the weight figures are liable to be somewhat uncertain.

From time to time all the patients are examined with Roentgen rays; radiograms are also taken in most cases. When the Roentgen examination or the radiogram do not add essentially to the information gained by the clinical examination, they are not quoted.

The principles of the treatment have been the hygienic measures usual in Sweden. For special details, see the Records. All the children were treated with quartz lamp.

The duration of the experiment has not been extended beyond three months, as the patients do not as a rule remain in the Sanatorium above that period.

The experiments are summarized in *Table 10* (p. 166).

The figures in the first row correspond to those in the Records. All odd numbers, which furthermore are accompanied by »Or.», refer to patients who have been given an orange. The even numbers are the patients, examined for the sake of control, who instead of the orange had a pastry.

The patient who in each couple must be regarded as decidedly the graver case of the two at the beginning of the experiment is indicated by an asterisk in the fifth row, where the stage of the disease is recorded. As the patients were chosen, the graver and the lighter case was every alternate time taken as control patient within each couple.

The progress is indicated, in the sixth row, by n, + and —, according to its being corresponding to what had been expected, better or worse than was expected.

In the seventh row, the progress of the orange case as compared to that of the control patient is indicated. The sign = means that both cases have shown a corresponding progress; +, that the orange case has progressed more favour-

ably, and —, that it has progressed less favourably than the control case.

From the sixth row is seen that out of 21 control cases 11 have progressed according to expectation, while 2 have progressed better and 8 worse. It must be borne in mind that the season in question, March—May, is the time of the year which is the most trying to tuberculosis patients. The death rate for tuberculosis is then at its highest. The rather bad results among the control patients are therefore not surprising and the favourable progress in those who have had the orange is the more noteworthy. Among 22 such patients, the progress has been as expected in 6 cases, while 16 have developed more favourably than might have been expected.

In the seventh row which indicates how within each couple the disease has progressed in the orange case, in comparison with the progress of the control case, we find that the orange case had a better course in 17 instances, similar in 3, and worse in 1 instance.

Criticism. Conclusion.

Several objections might be raised against this experiment, such as its dealing with too small a number of patients and too short a time. The first objection is irrelevant, as this has been only a primary experiment which must be repeated, and I hope will be repeated in different places and with a larger material. It will then be expedient to extend the experiment over a longer period, that is to say, begin earlier in the year. The time of conclusion is fixed for experiments of this kind, viz. the beginning of the early summer. A question which carries more weight is whether the experiments have been conducted with sufficient objectiveness. In the first place it may be brought into question whether the patients have not been subjected to a suggestive influence of the orange diet, an influence which might have improved the appetite and indirectly the process. Although counter-acting measures have been adopted, this possibility can not be entirely precluded. In the second place there is the question about the objective-

ness of the investigator. I have thought the best safe-guard in this respect would be to entrust the actual examination and the judgment of the patients to an experienced specialist, and to let my own opinion carry weight in opposition to his, only when in so doing I have caused the orange cases to have a less favourable or the control cases a more favourable verdict.

Another objection is that the dietary in the sanatorium already without the orange would contain a protective dose of antiscorbutic. This objection would have been more significant if the experiment had not given a clear evidence.

Conclusion. The experiment seems to indicate that the addition of an orange to the daily fare has favourably influenced the progress of tuberculosis with a number of patients in the Väsby Sanatorium during March—May 1923. The results encourage continued investigation on a larger scale in order to gain confirmation of the theory that a sufficient amount of antiscorbutic substance in the food strengthens the resistance against tuberculosis.

Summary and conclusions of Part IV.

A tuberculosis may in different ways act on the onset or the progress of scurvy. The appetite may diminish so that a sufficient dose of antiscorbutic is not consumed. The conditions of the intestine may become changed so that the consumed dose of antiscorbutic is prevented from having an effect. A scorbutic atrophy of the vascular wall may give clinical symptoms (hemorrhages) in the neighbourhood of tuberculous foci.

In a still higher degree a scurvy appears to act upon the progress of a tuberculosis. The clinical observations, which are recorded in the literature give good grounds for supposing such an action though they have not so far been duly considered. These observations lend countenance to the notion that the resistance of the body to tuberculosis is lessened during the course of scurvy. The experiments on man which

I have undertaken point in the same direction. Experiments on a larger scale are desirable especially in regions where, like in the Northern provinces of Sweden, the fresh vegetables are as rare as the tuberculosis is frequent.

My experiments on guinea-pigs indicate that a scorbutic organism has no power of reacting against a tuberculous focus with a connective-tissue formation of normal strength. The smaller the antiscorbutic dose in the food is, the less extensive and the more inferior in quality (fibrosity) the new connective tissue becomes. This diminished faculty of healing tuberculous foci through connective tissue is apparent already early in the latent stage, a fact which is of special interest.

This deficient reaction of the connective tissue to a tuberculous irritation agrees perfectly with what has been said in the preceding part of this work with regard to the scorbutic atrophy. I am far from wishing to attribute to this deficient development of fibrous tissue alone, or even principally, the influence of scurvy on the progress of tuberculosis. It is probable that the scorbutic atrophy of other cells in the body, which are important to the resistance, also is of account. As the benignity of a tuberculous process is often measured according to its more or less pronounced fibrosity, the change in this quality through scurvy, already in the latent stage, is yet worth observing.

From a therapeutic point of view it may be said that my investigations suggest the importance of supplying a sufficient fully protective antiscorbutic dose to persons, in whom the healing of a tubercular process is aimed at. This holds true also, and perhaps particularly, with regard to early forms, for instance tuberculosis of the bronchial glands in children. Since the standard of the fully protective dose of antiscorbutic for different ages has not yet been established, it may in dubious cases be recommended rather to give a little too much than too little of suitable antiscorbutic articles of food.

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